

APPLICATION OF DUCKWEED AS AN ALTERNATIVE IN POULTRY FEEDING*Guliyeva S.**Scientific Research Institute of Animal Husbandry
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Researcher of the "Breeding of ruminant cattle and small cattle, birds" laboratory***Abstract**

The wide use of hybrid birds in this field is the basis for keeping the growth rate of poultry farming at a high level and increasing it further. Hybrid birds are used to improve the breeding qualities of local indigenous bird breeds, enhancing and refining their most important biological and economic characteristics.

Keywords: Poultry, poultry, eggs, poultry meat, hybrid, feed supplement, Duckweed (duck grass) algae, macro-microelements, vitamins.

Introduction

The poultry industry continues to develop rapidly worldwide. After gaining independence, the Republic of Azerbaijan has been swiftly integrating into the global community. President Ilham Aliyev of the Republic of Azerbaijan has signed several decrees to ensure that the economy does not rely solely on the oil sector. As a result, the poultry sector in the country has embarked on a path of rapid development. [1].

At the end of the 20th century, the privatization process led to a significant leap in the poultry industry. The main reasons for this were the privatization of poultry farms, allowing entrepreneurs to use them, the reconstruction of existing farms, the construction of new modern factories, equipping them with very modern equipment, and the implementation of new progressive technologies.

Currently, due to the financial crisis in many countries and the sharp rise in food prices, the demand for poultry meat has increased significantly. It should be noted that pork still leads the meat production market, with poultry meat in second place. Worldwide, a total of 296 million tons of poultry meat is produced, with 37% pork and 34% poultry meat consumed annually by the population. [2]

In recent years, the import of hybrid birds, both meat-oriented and egg-laying, from foreign countries has been on the rise. Hybrid birds are used to improve the breeding qualities of local aboriginal bird breeds and to enhance their most important biological and economic characteristics. [3]

It is possible to meet the ever-increasing demand of the population for poultry meat and eggs by developing the poultry sector, one of the leading branches of animal husbandry, increasing the number of birds, and improving and refining their breeds.

Therefore, to maintain the productivity of the exotic chicken breeds brought to our country, it is essential to study their biological and economic characteristics in the zones where they are kept and to properly

carry out breeding and selection work to increase their overall productivity. [4]

The relevance of the research work: The scientific research work being conducted is relevant to meet the demand of our country's population for poultry products and to increase entrepreneurs' interest in this field. [1; 2].

Duckweed, as an autotrophic organism, is considered a potential food source for humans and animals. It is a very nutritious plant. Duckweed is useful as a natural food for wild animals, pets, and birds. [4].

Duckweed is recognized as a medicinal plant in bird feeding due to its unique chemical composition, richness in several macro and microelements, and vitamin content. It is widely used for the prevention and treatment of various diseases. [7].

Justification of the Topic: Recently, as in other fields of livestock, innovative technologies and the extensive use of various feed additives are being applied in bird feeding. There is a growing need for alternative feed sources, especially for egg-laying chicken breeds and newly created various directional lines. The feed intended for birds should be rich in macro-micro elements, vitamins, and biologically active substances. Since importing feed additives and premixes from foreign countries is expensive, it is possible to produce ecologically clean duckweed, which is grown in artificial conditions in water, mineral solutions, and can be used raw or dried after being washed in clean drinking water, ready for consumption. [8].

Considering the above, we propose using Duckweed grown in indoor conditions as an alternative feed source for birds.

Purpose and Objectives of the Research Study: The purpose of our research study is to investigate the application of Duckweed (a type of water algae) in the feeding of locally adapted, meat-producing poultry. This includes studying its effects on weight gain and meat quality.

Research Tasks and Methodology

Tasks: The task at hand involves the cultivation of Duckweed (a type of water algae) as a feed additive under laboratory conditions and its application in the feeding of productive poultry.

Methodology: The methodology of the research study is based on the poultry care technology approved by the All-Russian Scientific Research and Technological Poultry Institute (B.F. Bessarapov's "Technology for Poultry Meat and Egg Production Based on Industry" methodology, 2012) [3].

Research Object: The scientific research is conducted at the Poultry Farm of the Animal Science Research Institute. The research object consists of 10-45 day-old chicks from the Leader-55 broiler layer line.

Discussion of Research Results: During the research, experimental and control groups were established, each with 10 chicks. The control group was fed with standard feed, while the experimental group was fed with the sample feed. The chicks were fed with feed brought from the Agdash Feed Factory, including starter feed for days 1-20, grower feed for days 20-30, and finisher feed for days 35-45. In addition to the standard feeding regime, each chick received 10 grams of Duckweed (water algae) per day.

Table 1

Composition and Nutritional Value of the Main Feed for 35-45 Day-Old Birds, %, gr

Feeds	Amount of Feeds, %
Wheat	50,0
Corn	15,0
Corn-Sunflower Meal	10,0
Soybean Meal	19,0
Sunflower Oil	1,0
Mineral Feed and Vitamins	
Salt	0,3
Fish Meal	1,7
DKF	2,0
Premix	1,0
Nutritional Composition per 1 kg of Feed:	
Energy Value, MJ/kg	116,87
Energy Feed Unit	77,36
Crude Protein, %	7,74
Crude Fiber, %	18,7
Phosphorus, %	2,81
Calcium, %	0,7
Crude Fat, %	1,2
Feeds	2,81

Table 2

Composition and Nutritional Value of the Sample Feed

Feeds	Amount of Feeds, %
Wheat Bran	58,5
Mixed Feed	31,5
Duckweed (Algae)	10,0
Mineral Feed	
Lime	0,5
Marble Dust	0,5
Per 1 kg of Feed	
Feed Unit	113,68
Metabolizable Energy, MJ/kg	77,23
Energy Feed Unit	7,72
Crude Protein, %	18,45
Crude Fiber, %	1,26
Phosphorus, %	0,25
Calcium, %	0,52
Crude Fat, %	1,09

Body Measurements and Live Weight Gain of Birds at Various Ages, gr n=10

Groups 7 Days Old Control Experiment	Live mass gr	Heart		Length of the Breastbone, cm	Length of the Wingbone, cm
		width	girth		
14 Days Old Control Experiment					
21 Days Old Control Experiment	0,991	23,9	101	0,83	76,5
28 Days Old Control Experiment	1100	26,2	105	0,87	79
Groups					
7 Days Old Control Experiment	2220	37,5	118	76,5	100,5
14 Days Old Control Experiment	2400	40	122	79	112
21 Days Old Control Experiment					
28 Days Old Control Experiment	3690	56	183	95	117
Groups	4000	62	190	101	123
7 Days Old Control Experiment					
14 Days Old Control Experiment	5448	60	190	104	150
21 Days Old Control Experiment	5850	68	196	110	155

As seen from the table, during the 28-day period, the experimental group showed a higher increase in live weight compared to the control group. Considering the results obtained, it is possible to achieve comparative weight gain by using Duckweed (water lettuce) algae, grown under controlled conditions, as an alternative feed for poultry.

RESULT

In the conducted research, the following results were obtained for each bird:

1. **Weight Increase:** Birds fed with the experimental feed showed a higher weight gain compared to the control group. During the 28-day period, the body measurements of the control group were as follows: chest width 5 cm, chest circumference 18 cm, breastbone length 10 cm, wing bone length 17 cm, and live weight 635 grams.

2. **Experimental Group Measurements:** In the experimental group, the body measurements of each bird were as follows: chest width 7 cm, chest circumference 21 cm, breastbone length 12 cm, wing bone length 19 cm, and live weight 680 grams. The live weight of birds fed with the experimental feed was 45 grams higher than that of the control group.

3. **Live Weight Comparison:** By using Duckweed (water lettuce) algae as a feed supplement, a total of 402 grams more live weight was gained from 10 birds in the experimental group compared to the control group.

In the next phase, the application of Duckweed (water lettuce) algae in the feeding of poultry raised for meat production is planned to be studied for its impact on meat quality.

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